

STORYTELLING METHOD USED IN KINDERGARTEN CHILDREN.

Bahromova Munisa Otabekovna

Termez State University Foreign Philology Faculty the 2nd course student. @munisabahromova1@gmail.com , +99890 644 79 09
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ABSTRACT

Today, the pre-school education system is receiving more attention than any other area. Have you ever wondered why certain children seem extremely uninterested in story time? By using different storytelling methods, you may be able to capture their interest. Here are few ways to add a little variety to story time with your group.

Children, like adults, are always engaged in certain activities will be. Adults are a social utility that other people need If they are busy with the production of things, the main activity of children The purpose is based on learning. Even if children cannot yet write, they can still learn to tell stories. This is why oral storytelling practice is such a valuable tool for our emergent writers! Learning to tell stories with detail will help your students write with detail later on. Yet, with all the rich benefits, oral storytelling is often a skill that's skipped or not done enough in kindergarten and first grade. Storytelling with movement. Stories that involve movement make it possible for children to physically participate in the story. Encourage children to make a specific gesture when they hear a certain word or to perform various actions mentioned in the story. For example, in Little Red Riding Hood, children can pretend to carry baked goods in a basket, to be the wolf, or make a squeaking sound when a door is opened. To use wordless books for oral storytelling practice, have your students come up with the words to the story with you. Guide them to use vivid verbs! In the book Chalk, we used the word fluttered rather than flew, raced rather than ran, and melted rather than went away.

After retelling together a few times, reminding students of their new vivid words, have them practice telling their story orally to a partner. I created simple wordless books that kids can write in. These include familiar fairy tales, simple stories kids can relate to, life cycles, and how-to books. Special methods are used to teach children to tell stories. The story There are different ways of teaching. The most important of them is the educator to tell the example of the story, to make a plan of the story, to tell the story. It is the teacher's responsibility to make it part by part, to discuss its plan as a team are ways of asking questions, telling and evaluating children's stories. The teacher has one or two main methods for each training session chooses For example, telling a story pattern and plotting a story make a plan to make or tell a story and discuss the plan as a team can choose to do.

The teacher's example of storytelling is a didactic method, and his with the help of the teacher,

the teacher teaches children to tell stories by taking an example from others.

Children on a difficult type of story, that is, on the topic suggested by the teacher so that they can make up stories and these stories are different a teacher can use this method. Educator children the topic and plan will give. Topic: How did the little girl find the kitten?

1. How the little girl found the kitten.
- 2 How was the kitten?
3. What does the little girl do with it?

Children's answers on the spot will not be a story, it will be several or is one sentence. The goal is that stories can be different is to show. When the teacher is making a plan, it is best to discuss as a team difficult questions should be identified in advance. The example of telling a story should have a valuable educational content, it should make the children their own encouraging good behavior and friendship feelings in his stories must. The easiest way is to give a sample of the story. Because the children ask the tutor's questions about pictures, objects, events or they hear the finished story, not the instructions. Hence the story in the first stages of teaching to tell a story by the method of giving an example or used when the teacher sets new tasks for the children.

Plotting the story There are two main questions to follow when creating a story. In the story based on the experience of the common team, the teacher pre-planned the topic is divided into very small parts, for example, a pictorial on the topic "Our Hedgehog". When creating a story, the teacher tells the children everything about the hedgehog at once without speaking, warns that we will speak in order to remember everything. Then the educator gives a plan for each part. Now, children, remember the top of the hedgehog what is it covered with? What is his beak like? How does he walk? This plan will be transferred to another part after two or three children's stories. We have where the hedgehog lives, what is in his cage, why is he needed tell me After the children's answer, the story goes to the third part. Tell me what we fed the hedgehog. Who takes care of it, how? took care of, and at the end of the story, from the children, we gave our hedgehog to whom we gave a gift, what did the children of the middle group say to us? you can ask. Team for the story "In Kindergarten", "New Year's Tree", "To the Zoo", "excursion", "Tour around the city" and other topics can be selected.

At the end of the lesson, the educator is one in all parts of the subject 1-2 children who give a general plan and tell a good story about everything at once will tell. On speech development in the form of initial monologue in small group of children they use the picture widely. Children see the pictures during the training. Even in everyday life, look at the pictures in the book, photos, invitations they forgive Children in the first small group at the beginning of the year to the teacher's question they can answer in chorus. Educator helps children in time, he should say or answer together. Based on the education program in the middle group the content of teaching children to tell a story becomes somewhat complicated. Medium children of the group only retell well-known fairy tales and stories not only that, but also the works that were read for the first time during the training to tell a story, many objects, toys, plants, clothes are characteristic they should learn to describe their signs. Ability to retell well-known fairy tales and stories to children a literary work that has been read for the first time in a small group and the ability to tell a story begins to develop only in the middle group.

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